

THE INFLUENCE OF MATERNAL FOLKLORE ON THE DEVELOPMENT CHILDREN'S PERSONALITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13188362>

Annotation: The article investigates how maternal folklore influences a child's personality development. It concludes that children are naturally included as bearers of folk traditions from a young age

Key words: folklore, folk tale, lullaby, nursery rhymes, literature.

1 INTRODUCTION

In its literal English translation, the term "folklore" refers to folk or national wisdom. This is poetry created by and for the people, reflecting their work, society and daily life, knowledge of life, nature, culture, and faith. Folklore represents people's beliefs, standards, and desires, as well as their poetic imagination, a rich world of ideas, emotions, worries, dissatisfaction with exploitation and oppression, and dreams of a just and happy life. Folklore is an oral art form that includes sayings, tall stories, fairy tales, legends, myths, parables, tongue twisters, riddles, epic poems, and so on. Perceiving the works of people's folklore, children develop in all aspects, thus accomplishing the pedagogical tasks of upbringing, development, and education of each child.

Every parent wants their child to have a happy childhood, filled with fun, bright, and emotional memories that will last a lifetime. Adults can recreate such moments by using fairy tales, riddles, tongue twisters, counting rhymes, nursery rhymes, and a variety of other oral folklore. This is close and understandable to children.

Folklore accompanied people's daily lives, was an important part of everyday life, and brightened holidays while also assisting on weekdays. Rituals accompanied all events in people's lives, including the first plowing and the last sheaf gathering in the field in the autumn, youth celebrations, Christmas holidays and spring meetings, weddings, childbirth, and funerals. Throughout history, rituals have been linked to.

Folklore is an oral art form that includes sayings, tall stories, fairy tales, legends, myths, parables, tongue twisters, riddles, epic poems, and so on. Children's oral folklore takes on a special significance. Folk art inspires and attracts with its beauty and historical significance. However, it is always evolving, with new research and analysis being conducted. Native speech, as heard in fairy tales, eloquent intonations of Russian songs, and

colorful folk toys are essential tools for instilling in children a love of the world around them, which begins at birth. The Russian language, which children first learn through fairy tales and the expressive intonation of folk songs, is an important tool for teaching children to respect and care for their surroundings and one another. Children are naturally engaged as bearers of folk traditions from a young age.

The term "folklore" translates from English as folk or national wisdom. This is poetry created by and for the people, reflecting their work, society and daily life, knowledge of life, nature, culture, and faith. Folklore represents people's beliefs, standards, and desires, as well as their poetic imagination, a rich world of ideas, emotions, worries, dissatisfaction with exploitation and oppression, and dreams of a just and happy life.

Proverbs and sayings are a unique type of oral poetry that has absorbed many generations' works experience over the centuries. They used imagery to capture the experience of existence in all its complexities and inconsistencies.

Guessing and making riddles also help children develop their speech components. To create a metaphorical image in the riddle, various verbal expressions are used, such as epithets and comparisons. Riddles enrich the child's vocabulary due to word polysemy.

Nursery rhymes, tongue twisters, proverbs, and sayings help children develop a sense of rhythm and rhyme, as well as the formation of an expressive intonation in their speech.

Lullabies, nursery rhymes, and all songs that have passed from the adult repertoire to the children's repertoire (carols, ritual songs, and play songs); songs invented by children themselves are childhood songs composed by adults specifically for children.

Children's folklore also includes rhymes, jokes, tongue twisters, and fairy tales. A fairy tale is the most structured and adheres to specific rules. When telling

fairy tales, knowledge of special utterances is assumed, such as "Soon the fairy tale is told, but not soon the matter is done." At the same time, a fairy tale would be incomplete if the villain defeated the innocently persecuted people. Such an ending is common in fairy tales.

Children are given the foundations of cognitive activity; they develop visual and imaginative thinking, imagination, speech, experience improves their state of mind, and they gain the ability to perceive the world and act on their ideas. The development of generalized knowledge about objects and phenomena can be viewed as an important prerequisite for introducing children to their surroundings through maternal folklore. Guessing and inventing riddles also influences the versatile development of children's speech. Preschool children's imagery of speech is shaped by their use of expressive techniques such as impersonation, ambiguity, definitions, epithets, comparisons, and rhythmic organization when solving riddles.

Riddles help children expand their vocabulary, understand secondary meanings of words, and develop figurative concepts. They assist in assimilating the sound and grammatical structure of Russian speech, requiring them to focus on analyzing the linguistic form.

The riddle is a type of oral folk art that conveys vivid and figurative descriptions of objects or phenomena. Solving riddles improves analytical skills, allowing for independent drawing of conclusions and inferences, as well as highlighting expressive signs of an object or phenomenon and conveying images concisely, promotes a "poetic view of reality" in children.

People believe that lullabies are a companion for children. These genres, along with others, have a significant impact on preschool children's speech development.

Lullabies enhance children's vocabulary by providing information about the world around them, particularly about familiar and appealing objects.

The grammatical variety of lullabies helps to develop the grammatical structure of speech. These songs can be used to teach children how to form words from the same root because they create images that children are familiar with, such as a cat. Furthermore, it is not simply a cat, but a "kitten," "cat," or "kitty." Furthermore, positive emotions associated with one or more familiar ways from infancy help to ensure the success and longevity of this development.

A lullaby, a type of folk poetry, offers unique opportunities for developing phonemic perception. This is due to the use of vowel sounds, slow tempo, repetitive phonemes, and onomatopoeia. Lullabies help memorize words and phrases, improving lexical skills. Despite its

small volume, the lullaby offers endless educational opportunities.

Nursery rhymes, tongue twisters, proverbs, and sayings are excellent resources for fostering a strong speech culture. By instilling a sense of rhythm and rhyme in the child, we prepare him for further perception of poetic speech and shape his intonation. Folklore can help solve speech development problems for older preschoolers, alongside traditional methods and techniques. It is a valuable resource for enhancing verbal creativity. While the aforementioned work types are indicative, a comprehensive methodology for their implementation is still needed.

Folklore is an important part of raising children. Dividing it into genres allows children to enrich their spiritual world, develop patriotism, respect for the past, study traditions, and learn moral norms in society. Folklore influences a child's oral speech, spiritual development, and imagination. Each genre of children's folklore teaches specific moral values. Fairy tales teach children about social norms and foster imagination and ingenuity by depicting animals as humans. Proverbs and sayings have stood the test of time and continue to impart wisdom to children today. An epic is a heroic story set in antiquity. The epics aim to teach children about the people's past, traditions, and patriotism during the Mongol-Tatar yoke. Despite challenges, the people remained loyal to their homeland and defended it to the best of their abilities. Lullabies influence children's upbringing. It is typically used when the child is still very young.

CONCLUSION

Children are exposed to folk culture from a young age, learning fundamental concepts and behaviors. Cultural heritage is passed down through generations, shaping and enriching the child's world. Folklore is a unique way of passing down folk wisdom and raising children at the early stages of their development.

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